

ISic1179

Fragment of a Greek inscription

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

unknown

Material

stone

Object

fragmentary

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,system,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Recorded as beside the great door in the front of the Church of S. Maria dei Palazzi by Gualtherus, 1621-1624, and subsequently by Castelli, Principe di Torremuzza, who notes that it was dug up from the ruins of Halaesa.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, lost

Physical Description

Castelli, Principe di Torremuzza (1753: 147) notes that the stone was damaged on all sides

Dimensions

Height unknown cm

Width unknown cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

Remains to two lines of Greek letters, damaged at both ends (?)

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Gualtherus records the sigmas in line 2 and the epsilon in line 1 as lunate (and he is followed by Castelli)

Letter heights:

Line 1: unknown mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: unknown mm

Text

1. [---]IMN[]YATONΔEΠOIKIΛ[---]

2. [---]IXIII[]ΣΟΥΣΑΠΑΝΤΟΣΚΙ[---]

Apparatus

Text after Gualtherus and Castelli

Translation

Commentary

Gualtherus records the sigmas in line 2 and the epsilon in line 1 as lunate (and

he is followed by Castelli) and, assuming that this is an accurate record of what he saw, suggests a date of the imperial or late antique period. Kaibel speculated that it might be a verse text of the Byzantine period, reading τόνδε ποικίλ[ον] at the end of line 1, but despaired of interpretation. In similar vein, if correct, [-]υατον could be the end of a transliterated Latin name such as Torquatus, but the difficulty is that it is entirely possible that some of the letters are wrongly transcribed.

Digital identifiers:

TM 492784

EDCS 39102333

PHI 140662

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1179>

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.4021545](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4021545)

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0357 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Gualtherus, G. 1624. *Siciliae obiacentium insular. et Bruttiorum antiquæ tabulæ, cum animadversionib.* Messanae. At no.297

Castelli, Gabriele Lancillotto, principe di Torremuzza 1753. *Storia di Alesa, antica città di Sicilia.* Palermo. At 146 no.4

Castelli, Gabriele Lancillotto, principe di Torremuzza 1769. *Siciliae et obiacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio.* Panormus. At cl.18 no.27

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum.* Berlin. At 3.5599

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. *Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa.* Palermo. At no.50

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1179. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). [http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351733](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351733)

G. GUALTHERI

DEPERDITÆ. ET. QUÆ. OB. ABSENTIAM dominorum, aut alia obstacula aspici non potuerit

In ade Grefali. terra abilita

294
D. SEMPRONIO
7. L. PRIMIONI
ANNORVM. XVIII

In vineis. Lucis. apud Ant. Marchesium. calce abilitata

295
MAXIMO
IACONO
ET. N. Z

Maximo Iacone F. annorum LX

In maiori templo
296 STHENII AEDES

Legit Alph. Zappata veteram inscriptionem

CEPHALOEDIS

Ad portam Pifariam hinc fere forma

296
ΣΘΣΙΝΥΜΒΟΝ
ΚΡΑΦΑΤΕΚΑΙΡΕ

Sisymbon Craphate salus

D. MARIA. DE. PALATIO. seu. DE. PALATI
II. lapide à Thosa, opido Fran. Vicinillia Marchionis Hieracij

Sicut portam magnam in pariete

297
[IMN. . . TATONAE & DOXIAE]
[EXIII. . . COYCAPIANTOCKI]

298
IMP. CAESAREI
DIVI F
AVGVSTO PO.
MVNICIPIVM

Prope gradus, quibus ad aram maiorem a fovea dicitur in marmoreis. in hoc parte

299
GEOΣ ΠΑΞΙ
ΑΔΑΜΟΣ ΤΟΝ ΑΑΑΙΝΟΝ
ΙΟΥΕΝΝΗ ΔΙΟΥΕΝΝΟΣ
ΑΑΙΘΟΝΑ
ΝΕΠΤΕΛΙΑΣ . ΕΝΙΚΕΝ

Dico simul
populus H. al. gharum
Augustus Digenis P.
Lapideum
hinc dicitur causa

Copy of Gualtherus 1624 no.297 (from Arachne edition)